

CLIMATE RISK ASSESSMENT

Rio Branco, Brazil

MAY 2023

David Byrne, Foster Brown, Christopher Schwalm, Quéren Luna,
A. Willian Flores de Melo, Alan Pimentel, Rodrigo Santana, Sonaira Silva

For more information about this analysis, or Woodwell's other climate risk assessments, please contact us at policy@woodwellclimate.org.

To learn more about Woodwell, please visit our website at woodwellclimate.org.

Executive summary

1. Pollutants in the air we breathe are detrimental to human health. Long-term exposure to air particulate matter in Acre, Brazil, has decreased the average life expectancy by an estimated 2-3 years. Smoke from rural fires is the major source affecting air quality at Rio Branco.
2. Observations of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) have become available in Acre through the Purple Air project. Uncorrected data shows that in Rio Branco, an estimated 125 days exceeded the WHO's daily guidance for PM2.5 levels during the dry season in 2019.
3. Satellite observations indicate that rural fires are densely distributed around Rio Branco itself, North Rondônia, as well as northeastern and central Bolivia.
4. The source of the smoke arriving at Rio Branco within 6 days comes from nearby areas to the north and east (64% of the time), from the south (31% of the time) or from the east (5% of the time). The average 6-day air parcel spends half of its time inside a radius of just 266 km around Rio Branco.
5. Rural fires around Rio Branco are expected to increase due to changes in climate by 38% within 500 km by 2090, under the fossil fuel intensive IPCC scenario. Our analysis also shows that the number of smoke-producing rural fires within two days of wind transport of Rio Branco is expected to increase by a third by 2090. This does not include the effect of increased tree mortality in the region or changes in land cover and land use.
6. To improve air quality, fires must be reduced now from their present level.

1. Introduction

The air we all breathe

The air we breathe can have profound and long-lasting impacts on our health. Numerous pollutants, including ozone, nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and particulate matter, have been identified as potential contributors to a range of health impacts. Among these, of particular concern is the release of particulate matter into the air (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀). These microscopic particles can penetrate deep into the body, exacerbating serious conditions such as heart and lung disease, cancer, cognitive problems and susceptibility to COVID-19 (Sakhvidi et al., 2022, Mendy et al., 2021, Zhang et al., 2018, Xing et al., 2016, Kaufman et al., 2016).

A natural way to understand the impact of prolonged exposure to air pollution on public health is to consider its effect on life expectancy. Studies by Chen et al. (2013) and Ebenstein et al. (2017), alongside the University of Chicago AQLI project, have attempted to quantify this impact. Their findings indicate that an increase of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in PM₁₀ can reduce life expectancy by 0.64 years, while the corresponding reduction for PM_{2.5} is 0.98 years. Such long-term effects can exert substantial pressure on healthcare infrastructures, highlighting the importance for authorities to take measures to identify the sources of pollutants and minimize their presence in the air we breathe.

The World Health Organization has established guidelines to assist policymakers in determining safe levels of outdoor air pollution (World Health Organization, 2021). The 2021 guidelines recommend that the annual average concentrations of PM_{2.5} should not exceed 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 24-hour averages should not exceed 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for more than 3–4 days per year. Unfortunately, most of the world's population is not living in areas that satisfy these recommendations. Satellite-derived PM_{2.5} observations

from 2020 indicate that these guidelines are exceeded for 97.3% of the world's population (Greenstone et al., 2022), resulting in an estimated global loss of life expectancy of approximately 2.2 years per person, according to the AQLI dataset. This means that globally, air pollution poses a greater risk to human life than alcohol, firsthand smoking, malaria, or unsafe drinking water.

The introduction of particulate matter into the atmosphere commonly occurs through the combustion of biomass and fossil fuels, i.e., from motor vehicles, industry or rural fires. However, it is not necessary to live in close proximity to a pollutant source to be exposed to dangerous concentration levels. In fact, particulate matter may stay in the atmosphere for anywhere from minutes to weeks, depending on the properties of the particles (Esmen & Corn, 1971), meaning that smaller particulate matter such as PM_{2.5} can be carried by air currents for potentially hundreds of miles. In the case of high heat accompanying an emission source, such as with rural fires, large plumes can be generated, lifting particles high into the atmosphere and extending their range (Martin et al., 2012). Therefore, when analyzing air pollution risk, one must consider factors such as location, atmospheric flow, meteorological conditions, particle properties, and the source type.

Air pollution is a global issue that is not bound by international borders—the potential range of some pollutants means that air quality is a truly international and transnational issue. It is essential for nations to collaborate in an effort to understand both the sources and transport of pollutants. By working together, countries can take effective measures to safeguard public health for present and future generations.

Rio Branco and Amazonia

In this study, we assess present observations and make future projections of fire-related air quality for Rio Branco in the Brazilian state of Acre (see **Figures 1 and 2**). The state of Acre lies in the far west of Brazil, nestled amongst neighboring countries of Peru to the West, Bolivia to the South and the Brazilian states of Amazonas and Rondônia to the North and East. Rio Branco, the capital of Acre and a municipality of approximately 420,000 people, lies in the southeast of the state, less than 50 miles from both the international border with Bolivia and state border with Amazonas. Figure 2 shows land cover types according to the MODIS land cover dataset. Much of the area surrounding Rio Branco is occupied by rainforest (Evergreen Broadleaf Forest), especially to the north and the west. Acre itself is relatively flat and low lying, however the basin is bounded distantly in the west by the Andes Mountains, which controls much of the ground level atmospheric flow.

Figure 2. Rio Branco in the Brazilian state of Acre and surrounding states and countries. Colors show the land cover type according to the MODIS Land Cover dataset for 2020

Also apparent in **Figure 2** are the alterations left on the landscape by human influences and activities. The highways that connect settlements can be seen as lines of reduced forest cover and increased land cover types such as savanna and shrubland, e.g., extending out from Rio Branco to municipalities in the north and west of Acre. In some areas, the effects of deforestation can be seen, for example in the areas immediately surrounding Rio Branco and in much of Rondônia and Bolivia. Many of these areas have undergone significant deforestation in recent decades. According to Global Forest Watch (Global Forest Watch, 2023) and the Global Land

Analysis & Discovery (GLAD) dataset, this ranges from as much as 19% forest loss in Rondônia to 0.96% in Amazonas. Acre itself has seen 5.7% forest loss between 2000 and 2020. Forest loss for other surrounding regions is summarized in the table below.

Country / State	Tree Cover Loss
Rondônia	3.30 Mha (19%)
Acre	802 kha (5.7%)
Bolivia	3.32 Mha (5.6%)
Peru	762 kha (0.97%)
Amazonas	1.42 Mha (0.96%)

Human influences like deforestation are a significant driver of one of the primary contributors to air pollutants in the region: rural fire. Although rural fires can occur naturally (often initiated by a lightning strike), studies have shown that most fire events in many areas are related to human impacts (Balch et al., 2017). Deforestation can exacerbate the problem by reducing dense forest area, which holds moisture and humidity better than the less vegetated areas that replace them (Cardil et al., 2020). The probability of rural fire ignition and spread is also a function of meteorological variables such as precipitation, drought, temperature and wind speed. The Fire Weather Index (FWI) is a daily, unitless measurement which combines these meteorological variables in an attempt to account for the effects of fuel moisture and wind on the behavior of rural fires. The metric was developed by the Canadian Forest Service (Stocks et al., 1989) and has seen use globally in the prediction of rural fire risk. In a world of changing climates, meteorological risk factors may change in the future and the FWI is useful for making projections of this risk. Later in this report, we make use of the FWI to make such projections.

In the following sections, we present three analyses for Rio Branco:

1. First, we provide an overview of present day (2000–2020) air quality in Rio Branco and rural fires in the surrounding area (Section 2). This is done using satellite and ground level observing instruments which can record particulate matter concentrations. Rural fire spatial distributions are also estimated using satellite observations.
2. We simulate the trajectories of air parcels to estimate where air arriving at Rio Branco daily has been 6 days previously (Section 3).
3. We project upstream rural fire risk using the Fire Weather Index metric and machine learning (Section 4).

2. Present day air quality in Rio Branco

Air quality observations can be broadly categorized into two types: remotely-sensed data obtained from satellite observations, and in-situ data obtained from instruments on the ground. Each category has its own benefits and limitations.

1. **Remotely Sensed Observations.** Satellites are able to observe large areas, however their observations may have temporal inconsistencies. The orbital period of satellites, and cloudy days and night time reduce the effective time for monitoring. Despite this limitation, their data are used for obtaining low frequency averages over a region. Measurements of particulate matter are often derived from a satellite observed metric called Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD).
2. **In-situ measurements.** Conversely to remotely sensed observations, in-situ measurements provide on the ground data for a fixed location. However, they can do this at a very high frequency and report conditions that are often more relevant for the local communities, who breathe the air.

In a nutshell, in-situ measurements provide the best representation of local conditions, however they have spatial limitations. On the other hand, satellite observations can fill in the spatial gaps but with temporal limitations. Often, spatially and temporally “complete” datasets can be created by combining both types of observations with estimates from computer simulations using a technique called data assimilation.

Figure 3 shows a selection of time series of PM_{2.5} concentrations across Acre between the years 2000 and 2018. Location specific data (at Rio Branco and Cruzeiro do Sul) is taken from a gridded dataset created by the University of Washington St. Louis (van Donkelaar et al., 2021). This data estimates surface PM_{2.5} at the monthly level by combining satellite AOD, simulations using a chemical transport model and ground-based observations where available. The figure also shows the annual average across all of Acre, which is what is used in the life expectancy estimates from the AQLI dataset mentioned in Section 1.

Figure 3(a) shows monthly mean PM_{2.5} concentrations at the two locations in Acre. The data shows a seasonal cycle in PM_{2.5} at both locations, which aligns well with the fire season (July–November), suggesting that this signal is primarily driven by rural fires. Annual peaks are higher every year in Rio Branco than in Cruzeiro do Sul, as shown in **Figure 3(c)**. **Figure 3(b)** shows the annual mean PM_{2.5} levels at each location and across all of Acre. Despite some annual variability, all annual averages exceed the WHO guideline threshold of 5 µg/m³ per year. Using the AQLI life expectancy loss estimates, this translates into an average loss of life expectancy in Acre of 2.7 years, equating to a total loss of approximately 2.5 million years of life¹.

¹ With an estimated 2021 population of 906,876 in Acre.

Figure 3. PM_{2.5} observations derived from satellite measurements at Rio Branco, Cruzeiro do Sul and averaged across all of Acre. **Top:** Monthly mean measurements, **Middle:** Annual mean measurements. **Bottom:** Annual maxima of monthly mean time series. Data is taken from the Donkelaar (University of Washington St Louis) dataset.

The AQLI dataset is a powerful tool for quantifying the impacts of air pollution. However, further study is needed to quantify the long term health effects of air pollution, especially particulate matter. The studies used in the AQLI project focus on urban populations in China, and the results here have been extrapolated globally. More localized assessments of air quality health impacts are relatively limited however.

The previously discussed limitations of satellite data place constraints on how finely resolved the above measurements can be spatially. The resulting averaging scales mean that the data may not perfectly represent the air that is actually being breathed by someone in Rio Branco. For this, we need high frequency consistent in-situ measurements. Historically, such observations for Rio Branco and surrounding regions have been scarce. However, recent funding allowed for the installation of a number of in-situ instruments to be a part of the Purple Air network (<https://www2.purpleair.com>). These instruments have been recording high frequency particulate matter concentrations at a number of locations around Acre, including Rio Branco since 2018.

Figure 4 shows examples of time series taken from 4 of these locations: two near Cruzeiro do Sul and two near Rio Branco. The values shown are raw data and uncorrected to account for calibration errors. The locations of the available Purple Air sensors in Acre are also shown. It is clear from the figure that, in the raw data, the WHO guidelines for daily concentrations (shown by the red dashed line) are frequently exceeded. For example, In 2019 there are 125 days exceeding $15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 4. Examples of high frequency observations of PM_{2.5} from four Purple Air sensors in Acre. The available sensor locations in Acre, as of 30th March 2023, are shown in the right panel. On the left, the top row shows data for near Cruzeiro do Sul and the bottom shows data for near Rio Branco. Red dashed lines show the WHO guidelines for daily PM_{2.5} concentration levels.

3. Where is the smoke coming from?

When considering the source of the smoke that arrives at Rio Branco, there are a number of separate questions to consider. Two of the most important are discussed in the following sections.

3.1 Where are the rural fires?

For this section, we need observations of rural fire events. In this study, we have used the FiredPy fire event delineation model (Balch, 2020) to define fire event polygons using MODIS burned area data (Giglio, 2018). The MODIS product uses satellites to identify where and when burning has occurred at a resolution of 500 m. The FiredPy system then ingests this data to identify distinct fire events, including a geospatial shape of fire, ignition location, total burned area and burn rates. We can analyze this data to determine spatial distributions of fire in the study area.

Figure 5. Gridded fire distributions. Each value shows the number of fire events per year within a 1/4-degree grid box according to MODIS burned area data and the FiredPy event identification model.

Figure 5 shows the number of fire events per year (according to ignition location), as observed by the MODIS data, within 1/4-degree grid cells. The distribution is shown for our study area: Bolivia, Peru and the Brazilian states of Acre, Amazonia and Rondônia. It is important to consider a large area in this analysis as the potential range of particulate matter can be large, as discussed in Section 1. Many of the patterns we see in this data are closely associated with the land cover distribution shown in Figure 2, for example:

- Fire events are observed most abundantly in less vegetated regions (e.g., savanna, shrubland, grassland) around Rio Branco, across to Porto Velho and in central

Bolivia. Many of these areas have undergone significant deforestation.

- North and west of Rio Branco, moving into Peru and Amazonas, we see fewer fire events and these regions are generally much more heavily forested. This may be due to a combination of reduced human influence and better moisture retention than shrublands or savanna-like areas.
- A small number of fire events follow alongside natural features such as the Amazon River and its tributaries, indicating the presence of human influence.
- Areas described as the “bare” land cover type such as southwest Bolivia or coastal Peru see very few to no fire events at all. This makes sense as there isn’t the biomass to burn in these areas.

3.2 Where does the smoke go?

Understanding how emissions travel through the atmosphere from the locations depicted in Figure 5 is crucial, particularly in determining the likelihood of pollutants reaching Rio Branco. Most importantly, we need to know how likely emissions are to reach Rio Branco. In this study, we employed the HYSPLIT (Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory) model developed by NOAA (Stein, 2015) to simulate the pathways that air parcels take before reaching Rio Branco. HYSPLIT's trajectory mode functions by treating an air parcel as a single particle that is suspended and carried through the atmospheric flow. This atmospheric flow is three-dimensional and provided by the user. For this analysis, we have used the "backwards" mode of HYSPLIT, to push the particle through a reversed flow. Instead of being pushed forward from Rio Branco by the atmospheric winds, we reverse the wind direction to see where it is likely to have come from. These backwards trajectories are simulated for six days prior to arrival at 50 m above Rio Branco.

To accurately model the movement of air parcels, we utilize the GDAS (Global Data Assimilation System) 1-degree atmospheric data. This dataset contains all necessary atmospheric variables at multiple vertical levels. While a higher resolution may be necessary for more localized analyses, 1-degree resolution is sufficient for our purposes. For our analysis, we calculate one backwards trajectory per day between 2000 and 2018 for the months of August to November, which corresponds to the height of the fire season. In total, we have approximately 2200 trajectories to analyze. More information about the setup and testing of our HYSPLIT model can be found in Appendix C.

We employ two methods for this analysis: clustering and density analysis. Trajectory clustering allows us to simplify our large ensemble of trajectories by identifying a smaller number of clusters, i.e. trajectories that have similar behaviors. A density analysis calculates how many trajectory data points we have in a set of grid boxes, allowing us to see which areas are most commonly traversed by modeled air parcels.

Figure 6(a) shows the full ensemble of daily trajectories and **Figure 6(b)** shows the average trajectories of each cluster identified by the HYSPLIT clustering algorithm. The percentage of all trajectories represented by each cluster is also provided. Although there are seven clusters, this analysis shows three main patterns:

- **A slow relatively local flow from the north and the east.** Most of the trajectories reaching Rio Branco in six days come from within 1000 km and have traveled from the North, over Acre and Amazonas or from the northeast. These account for approximately 64% of all trajectories reaching Rio Branco.
- **A fast flow up from the south, partially controlled by the Andes mountains.** The algorithm identified four such clusters, which travel over very similar areas but at varying speeds. Colors in the figure are simply used to distinguish these trajectories. In total, these clusters account for approximately 31% of air trajectories arriving at Rio Branco.
- **A fast and widespread flow from the east.** Approximately 5% of air parcels arriving at Rio Branco come quickly from the east. There is a large latitudinal spread in this cluster however.

Figure 6. 20 years of 6-day backward trajectories released from Rio Branco. **a)** The full ensemble of trajectories. Each blue line shows a single daily trajectory. **b)** Clustered trajectories and their percentage contributions to the total ensemble. Colors are only used to distinguish different trajectories.

Figure 7(a) shows the percentage of all trajectories that passed over each grid cell at least once. This data can be thought of intuitively by asking the question: for an air parcel arriving at Rio Branco on any day during the fire season, what is the probability that it passed over any given grid cell (for at least one hour) during the previous six days? In the data, we see a clear spatial skew in the trajectory distribution, approximately oriented between NNW and SSE. Here, we are seeing the controlling effect of the Andes mountains on the local atmospheric flow. Generally, the most well-defined regimes follow that of the cluster analysis above, with trajectories coming from a large and nearby area north of Rio Branco, or approaching quickly from the south. Very few to no trajectories come from Peru, especially past the Andes mountains, or southwest Bolivia.

Figure 7(a) gives us no information about where most of the air is spending its time before arriving at Rio Branco. Each grid square tells us how many trajectories passed over for at least one hour, but if a trajectory spends all of its time at that location it only counts once. Trajectories can move at different speeds on their six-day journey to Rio Branco, with some moving very little distance at all and others traveling 1000s of miles. **Figure 7(b)** shows the percentage of time spent across all trajectories in each grid box. Broadly speaking, this shows where air parcels arriving at Rio Branco spent their time during the previous six days. Many of the structures seen in this data are similar to those in Figure 7(a), however there are subtle differences. The data is weighted more to the large region north of Rio Branco than to the southern trajectories because of the slower moving nature of the northern air. The dashed line in the figure shows the radius around Rio Branco in which 50% of this distribution lies.

Figure 7. Gridded distributions of 20 years of backwards trajectories from Rio Branco. **a)** The percentage of trajectories passing over each grid square. **b)** The proportion of all simulated time spent over each grid square.

4. The future of Rio Branco

The drivers of fire-related air quality, both human and meteorological, are expected to undergo significant changes in the future. Deforestation is likely to continue, human activity will keep increasing, and global warming will cause changes in precipitation, drought, wind, and temperature. In this section, we present two approaches to help us predict increases in the number of upstream fires around Rio Branco due to changes in climate conditions. The first is the Fire Weather Index and fire danger days, an existing concept that we discuss in Section 4.2. We then extend this metric to include land-based variables such as land cover and human influence in Section 4.3. In this section, we also introduce the concepts of radial and upstream events for Rio Branco.

4.1 Quantifying fire impact: Radial and upstream analyses

The fire risk projections in this section have been analyzed for the whole study region, i.e. Acre, Amazonas, Rondônia, Peru, and Bolivia. However, increased fire risk in some areas may have more impact on air quality in Rio Branco than in others. To assess these impacts, we have adopted a “radial” and “upstream” approach. A radial event refers to an occurrence within a fixed radius around Rio Branco. We can calculate changes within these radii by analyzing the two-dimensional distributions of fire counts. The radii used are 266 km, 532 km, and 1064 km, based on the radii defined in Section 3’s analysis.

The radial approach does not take into account the patterns of atmospheric flow presented in Section 3. Therefore, we combine our fire projections with the trajectory percentage dataset (the percentage of trajectories passing over each grid point—see Figure 7(a)). For a single location, we can estimate statistically how many fire events per year are passed over by a trajectory that ultimately arrives at Rio Branco (an **upstream event**). To do this, we multiply the trajectory percentage at this location with the number of events per year. For example, suppose a location sees 10% of all trajectories pass over it within six days of reaching Rio Branco and this location is also projected to have 20 additional fires per year in 2050. On average, this location would contribute two additional fire danger days in Rio Branco’s upstream flow. By performing this calculation at every location and summing across the whole region, we obtain an estimate of the number of “upstream” events for Rio Branco. Mathematically, this is equivalent to taking the dot product of the two datasets.

We can apply this approach to varying time windows for trajectories at Rio Branco. Below, we present results for three time windows: 0–2 days upstream, 2–4 days upstream and 4–6 days upstream.

4.2 Upstream fire danger days

In Section 1 we introduced the Fire Weather Index, a daily, unitless measurement of fire danger, derived from temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and precipitation. It is useful to assess fire risk in terms of changes in the number of “fire danger days.” A fire danger day is defined as any day with an FWI value in the highest 5% of values at each location, i.e., a 1-in-20 day occurrence. This threshold indicates a high-danger fire day, where fires have the potential to quickly grow out of control in the event of natural or human-caused ignition. Then, we can assess how risk changes in the future by counting the number of days with an FWI value greater than these historical extremes. In other words, we take the value of the highest 5% of FWI values at every location for the 2000–2020 period, and count how many times this is exceeded under future time periods.

In the analysis below, we use FWI data derived from three CMIP5 models dynamically downscaled using REMO2015, for the IPCC RCP85 scenario. This data is bias adjusted and statistically downscaled to 1/4-degree resolution. Bias adjustment is done relative to ERA5 (Vitolo et al., 2020), a historical gridded dataset that incorporates observations. Performing this adjustment means that the bias in the CMIP5 data and ERA5 data will match for the historical period, which in our case is 2000–2020. Statistical downscaling allows us to obtain a higher resolution dataset.

Figure 8 shows the change in FWI danger days for 2040–2060 and 2070–2090 around our study region. We see the number of danger days either stay approximately the same or increase in both time periods. Generally, increases are larger for the late century time period. In some areas this increase is significant, reaching over 100 additional days per year in Northeast Amazonas and low-lying regions of Peru. In the areas immediately surrounding Rio Branco however, these increases are generally small.

Figure 8. The change in fire danger days per year relative to 2000–2020 in two future periods according to CMIP5 projections under the RCP85 IPCC scenario. A fire danger day is defined as a value of Fire Weather Index exceeding the 95th percentile at each location for the reference period.

Increases in fire danger days may lead to increases in the number of fires and therefore concentration of particulate matter. **Figure 9(a)** shows the percentage increase in the number of area total fire danger days within three radii around Rio Branco. Within the smallest radius, we see increases of 26% and 75% for the 2040–2060 and 2070–2090 time periods respectively. For all radii, the number of fire danger days increases towards the end of the century. Larger radii see larger increases, which agrees well with the data in Figure 8, i.e. as we move further from Rio Branco, we see large increases in the number of fire danger days.

Figure 9(b) shows the projected increases in the number of upstream fire danger days for 0–2, 2–4 and 4–6 days upstream. Similarly to the radial analysis, we see an increase towards the end of the century and the further we move from Rio Branco.

Figure 9. Percentage increases in the area sum number of FWI fire danger days **a)** within 3 different radii around Rio Branco and **b)** upstream from Rio Branco.

4.3 Extending FWI using Machine Learning

The Fire Weather Index is an effective tool for evaluating fire risk, but it alone does not provide complete insight into the likelihood of fires. This is due to the fact that fire ignition is influenced not only by weather, but also by factors such as land cover, land use, and human activity. Furthermore, fire danger days are not an absolute measure of risk as they depend on a specific baseline period for each location. To improve upon using FWI danger days, we have developed a machine learning model that incorporates these additional factors to enhance the FWI.

A machine learning model is a powerful tool that can learn from historical data and make predictions based on new inputs. In our case, we want to predict fire occurrence and its probability using variables such as FWI and landcover. Machine learning models must be “trained” or “fit” to the data that we have, then they can then be applied to provide predictions using new inputs. Below, we give a brief description of the model here but see Appendix-A for more details on the methodology behind this model.

We develop our model to output the probability of daily fire ignition within 0.25×0.25 grid cells. Inputs to the model are FWI, the proportion of 17 land cover types within each cell from the MODIS dataset, human footprint data (Venter, 2018), WGLC lightning density dataset (Kaplan, 2021), mean elevation from the SRTM30 dataset, and latitude. We use a gridded version of the FiredPy fire event locations to determine whether there was a fire event within a given grid cell on a given day. In other words, we provide the trained model with all of the above information and it will attempt to give us a probability that a fire event started on that day. Once we have applied the model for every day and location in the study region, we sum daily probabilities for each year to obtain expected annual counts of fire events for each grid cell. For example, if a single grid point has a $1/365$ chance of ignition for every day in the year, we would expect there to be one event per year (on average) at that location. A separate model is developed for Peru, Bolivia and three Brazilian states to account for social and political differences.

Training of the model is done using FWI data from the ERA5 dataset (Vitolo, 2020) for 2000–2018. It is important to assess how accurately the model predictions are. To evaluate this, we train the model on a subset of the data and compare its predictions to

another subset that it has never seen before. Our analysis shows that 90% of predictions are within 15% of the true distribution. That is, if the model predicts a daily probability of 10%, the actual observed distribution is between 8.5%-11.5% with 90% confidence. Once the models are trained, we use FWI data derived from three CMIP5 model runs to obtain projected annual fire counts up to the year 2100. This is done for the IPCC RCP85 model scenario.

Figure 10 shows radial counts and upstream counts for the three radii and upstream time periods. Here we see relatively little change for all time periods in the number of upstream fires until around the year 2050. However, after this point, the number increases rapidly. By 2090, our model predicts that the number of annual fires will have increased by 34% two days upstream of Rio Branco and 40% for 2-6 days upstream. The radial counts show a very similar pattern, with a sudden acceleration in 2050. Generally, larger increases tend to be in the same locations as high present-day counts. Broadly speaking, this matches up with the data shown in Figure 8. For 2050, increases in FWI danger days are small in the areas around Rio Branco but increase significantly by 2090.

Figure 10. Percentage changes in the number of fires at Rio Branco according to climatological projections (RCP85) of FWI and machine learning. **a)** The percentage change within three annuli concentric around Rio Branco. **b)** The percentage change in 6-day upstream fires.

5. Further discussion & conclusions

Air quality is critical for public health, making it a primary driver for research. In Section 2 of this study, we touched upon an important metric for quantifying the impact of air pollution on public health: its impact on life expectancy. Based on data from University of Chicago Air Quality Life Index (AQLI) project, it is estimated that meeting World Health Organization guidelines could save 2-3 years of life expectancy per person in Acre. This highlights the importance of reducing air pollution to improve the quality of life for everyone in the community.

AQLI life expectancy estimates were made using annual mean observations of PM_{2.5} across all of Acre. However, in Section 2, we demonstrated that observations on a monthly frequency can significantly vary across the state. For instance, the south (near Rio Branco) experiences more fire occurrences than the North (near Cruzeiro do Sul), resulting in higher seasonal peaks. Understanding how air quality varies across Acre is vital for understanding impacts on public health.

We showed that we can use gridded datasets derived from combinations of models and observations to estimate these spatial variations. However, such datasets can lack accuracy in areas where observations are sparse. The most reliable way to get locally representative observations is through well maintained in-situ instrumentation, such as those presented in Section 2, extracted from the Purple Air database. The state of Acre has made great progress recently in installing and maintaining such in-situ instruments and it is highly recommended that this continues.

The accessibility of air quality data to all communities, including indigenous communities, farmers, researching and decision-makers, is crucial. While the Purple Air website provides some level of accessibility, the data processing is minimal, and it is not tailored for the region. Willian de Flores (Universidade Federal do Acre) has developed a website (<http://www.acrequalidadedoar.info>), that displays processed air quality data from the Purple Air database that is bespoke for Acre. The website offers air quality information in the Portuguese language by municipality in Acre, comparisons to World Health Organization guidelines, color-coded risk levels, and explanations of the data. It has seen success in Acre and could serve as a prototype template for other regions seeking to improve access to real-time air quality data.

Using the HYSPLIT model, we identified three major regimes for air parcels arriving at Rio Branco. Our analysis reveals that approximately 31% of trajectories approach quickly from the south, 64% from the nearby areas to the north and east, and a smaller 5% from the East. This data is useful for identifying areas that are “upstream” of Rio Branco, and with what frequency. Understanding the source of air arriving in the region is a crucial step towards reducing the impact of smoke on all communities. For example, our analysis shows that across all modeled trajectories, half of the total modeled time was spent within just 266 km of Rio Branco. The 31% of air parcels arriving from the south are also likely to contribute to the quality of air in Acre. Despite making up a smaller proportion of the modeled trajectories, our analysis using the FiredPy model shows more underlying fire events. As some of this air and many of these fires are occurring in Bolivia, this shows the importance of regional communities and authorities working together to reduce these emissions. However, despite the higher fire event density to the south, we emphasize that most air parcels are carrying the impacts of nearby areas, meaning that it is future decisions made within Brazil—for example around deforestation, urbanization and fire control policies—that could have significant consequences for Rio Branco. Conducting

similar trajectory analyses with HYSPLIT in other locations surrounding Acre and neighboring countries is an essential next step.

Managing and understanding the impact of fire-related air quality in Rio Branco and Acre is increasingly important for the future. Our analyses suggest that by 2090, there could be an increase of 34% in the number of fires occurring within 0-2 days atmospherically upstream of Rio Branco, and 40% for areas within 2-6 days. These increases could lead to a significant rise in particulate matter concentrations, with adverse effects on public health. Furthermore, these changes are due to meteorological changes only, and do not consider possible changes in land cover, land use and human influence. If current trends in land use continue, then these projections are likely to be an underestimate in the context of the climate scenario used in this study (RCP85). Therefore, our projections should be used as a conservative estimate of future upstream fire risk under a high-emissions scenario.

References

- Balch, J. K., Bradley, B. A., Abatzoglou, J. T., & Mahood, A. L. (2017). Human-started wildfires expand the fire niche across the United States. *PNAS*, 114(11), 2946-2951. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1617394114>
- Balch, J. K., St. Denis, L. A., Mahood, A. L., Mietkiewicz, N. P., Williams, T. M., McGlinchy, J., & Cook, M. C. (2020). FIRED (Fire Events Delineation): An Open, Flexible Algorithm and Database of US Fire Events Derived from the MODIS Burned Area Product (2001-2019). *MDPI*, 12(21), 3498. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12213498>
- Cardil, A., de-Miguel, S., Silva, C. A., Reich, P. B., Calkin, D., Brancalion, P. H. S., Vibrans, A. C., Gamarra, J. G. P., Zhou, M., & Pijanowski, B. C. (2020). Recent deforestation drove the spike in Amazonian fires. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(12), 121003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abcac7>
- Chen, T. G. (2016). XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System. *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, New York, NY, USA*, 785-794. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1603.02754>
- Chen, Y., Ebenstein, A., Greenstone, M., & Li, H. (2013). Evidence on the impact of sustained exposure to air pollution on life expectancy from China's Huai River policy. *PNAS*, 110(32), 12936-12941. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1300018110>
- Ebenstein, A., Fan, M., Greenstone, M., & Zhou, M. (2017). New evidence on the impact of sustained exposure to air pollution on life expectancy from China's Huai River Policy. *PNAS*, 114(39), 10384-10389. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1616784114>
- Esmen, N. A., & Corn, M. (1971). Residence time of particles in urban air. *Atmospheric Environment*, 5(8), 571-578. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981\(71\)90113-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981(71)90113-2)
- Giglio, L., Boschetti, L., Roy, D. P., Humber, M. L., & Justice, C. O. (2018). The Collection 6 MODIS burned area mapping algorithm and product. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 217, 72-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.08.005>
- Global Forest Watch. (2023, April 7). Global Forest Watch: Forest Monitoring, Land Use & Deforestation Trends. Retrieved April 7, 2023, from <https://www.globalforestwatch.org>
- Greenstone, M. H., Hasenkopf, C., & Lee, K. (2022). *Air Quality Life Index: June 2022 Annual Update*. University of Chicago.
- Kaplan, J. O., & Lau, K. H. (2021). The WGLC global gridded lightning climatology and time series. *Earth System Science Data*, 13(7), 3219-3237. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-3219-2021>
- Kaufman, J. D., Adar, S. D., Barr, R. G., Budoff, M., Burke, G. L., Curl, C. L., Daviglius, M. L., Roux, A. V. D., Gassett, A. J., Jacobs Jr, D. R., Kronmal, R., Larson, T. V., Navas-Acien, A., Olives, C., Sampson, P. D., Sheppard, L., Siscovick, D. S., Stein, J. H., Szpiro, A. A., & Watson, K. E. (2016). Association between air pollution and coronary artery calcification within six metropolitan areas in the USA (the Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis and Air Pollution): a longitudinal cohort study. *Lancet*, 388(10045), 696-704. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)00378-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)00378-0)
- Martin, M. V., Kahn, R. A., Logan, J. A., Paugam, R., Wooster, M., & Ichoku, C. (2012). Space-based observational constraints for 1-D fire smoke plume-rise models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D22). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012JD018370>

- Mendy, A., Wu, X., Keller, J. L., Fassler, C. S., Apewokin, S., Mersha, T. B., Xie, C., & Pinney, S. M. (2021). Air pollution and the pandemic: Long-term PM_{2.5} exposure and disease severity in COVID-19 patients. *Respirology*, 26(12), 1181-1187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/resp.14140>
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. (2023, April 7). *HYSPLIT Clustering Equations*. *HYSPLIT Online Documentation*. https://www.ready.noaa.gov/documents/Tutorial/html/traj_cluseqn.html
- Sakhvidi, M. J., Yang, J., Lequy, E., Chen, J., de Hoogh, K., Letellier, N., Mortamais, M., Ozguler, A., Vienneau, D., Zins, M., Goldberg, M., Berr, C., & Jacquemin, B. (2022). Outdoor air pollution exposure and cognitive performance: findings from the enrolment phase of the CONSTANCES cohort. *Lancet Planet Health*, 6(3), e219-e229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00001-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00001-8)
- Stein, A. F., Draxler, R. R., Rolph, G. D., Stunder, B. B., Cohen, M. D., & Ngan, F. (2015). NOAA's HYSPLIT atmospheric transport and dispersion modeling system. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 96(12), 2059-2077. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00110.1>
- Stocks, B. J., Lawson, B. D., Alexander, M. E., Van Wagner, C. E., McAlpine, R. S., Lynham, T. J., & Dubé, D. E. (1989). The Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System: An Overview. *The Forestry Chronicle*, 65(6). <https://doi.org/10.5558/tfc65450-6>
- van Donkelaar, A., Hammer, M. S., Bindle, L., Brauer, M., Brook, J. R., Garay, M. J., Hsu, N. C., Kalashnikova, O. B., Kahn, R. A., Lee, C., Levy, R. C., Lyapustin, A., Sayer, A. M., & Martin, R. V. (2021). Monthly Global Estimates of Fine Particulate Matter and Their Uncertainty. *Environmental Science & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c05309>
- Venter, O., Sanderson, E. W., Magrath, A., Allan, J. R., Beher, J., Jones, K. R., Possingham, H. P., Laurance, W. F., Wood, P., Fekete, B. M., Levy, M. A., & Watson, J. E. (2018). *Last of the Wild Project, Version 3 (LWP-3): 2009 Human Footprint, 2018 Release*. Palisades, New York: NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC). <https://doi.org/10.7927/H46T0JQ4>
- Vitolo, C., Di Giuseppe, F., Barnard, C., Coughlan, R., San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., Libertá, G., & Krzeminski, B. (2020). ERA5-based global meteorological wildfire danger maps. *Scientific Data*, 7(216). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0554-z>
- World Health Organization. (2021). *WHO global air quality guidelines: particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide*. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO: World Health Organization.
- Xing, Y.-F., Xu, Y.-H., Shi, M.-H., & Lian, Y.-X. (2016). The impact of PM_{2.5} on the human respiratory system. *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, 8(1), E69-E74. <https://doi.org/10.3978/j.issn.2072-1439.2016.01.19>
- Zhang, X., Chen, X., & Zhang, X. (2018). The impact of exposure to air pollution on cognitive performance. *PNAS*, 115(37), 9193-9197. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1809474115>

Appendices & Methods

A. Developing the fire machine learning model

Objective: Develop a machine learning model to produce daily probabilities of fire ignition and estimates of annual ignition counts per year under present and future climates. Here, we describe the details and validation of the model.

Model: XGBoost (Chen, 2016). This is a version of gradient boosting (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gradient_boosting), which aims to create an optimal decision tree. It is able to handle imbalanced data well (ours has a ratio of 1 ignition per 250 data samples on average). We implement it using the XGBoost Python package (<https://xgboost.readthedocs.io/en/stable>).

Training data and output: The model is trained to estimate daily probabilities of ignition given a set of daily inputs (although not all variables are changing on a daily basis). The output used to train the model is a daily gridded ignition product derived using the FiredPy fire event model and MODIS burned area data. This dataset consists of a 1/4 x 1/4 degree grid, with a daily boolean at each location defining whether or not there was a FiredPy ignition on that day. These ignition locations are mapped to the nearest grid cell in an array with dimensions (time x longitude x latitude). The resulting array is a sparse integer array, where a 1 signifies an ignition on that day and location. This is a classification task, i.e., the model is trained to provide the probability that a sample belongs to one of two classes: ignition or no ignition. Output is defined on a 0.25 x 0.25 degree grid. So probabilities are “the chance of ignition on a given day within a 0.25 x 0.25 degree box.”

Daily probabilities can be used to obtain longer term metrics such as the number of ignitions per year/return periods and annual spatial ignition distributions. Daily probabilities can be converted to expected annual counts by simply summing them at each location in the domain. For example, if a grid point sees a daily ignition probability of 1/365 for every day, then we would expect to see one ignition per year on average.

Tuning: Grid search cross validation with three folds is used to tune the model hyperparameters. We use ROC AUC as a training metric, which is better than more common metrics such as accuracy when working with imbalanced data. When tuning the model, a balance must be made between the best score (highest ROC) and how long the model takes to train. In other words, in some cases, small improvements might be made in the ROC AUC, however will triple the training time. This may not be a worthwhile improvement.

Calibration: We calibrate our model using isotonic regression.

Features (Inputs)

Feature Set	# Features	Description
Fire Weather Index (FWI)	1	<p>FWI is a dimensionless index derived using atmospheric variables which describes fire risk.</p> <p>For model training, FWI is derived from ERA5 reanalysis data. For future projections, it is derived from CMIP5 data.</p> <p>Daily mean values of FWI are used in the model. Where the ignition grid is different from the FWI grid, a bilinear interpolation is used to regrid the data.</p>
Landcover Type	Up to 17	<p>Whether an area is dominated by trees or shrubs, water or urban areas can have an influence on ignition probability. We use the MODIS landcover dataset, which has a resolution of 500m and 17 landcover classes (when using the classification).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Transformation: proportion for each landcover class within the grid cells of the ignition grid. The result is up to 17 different features, each having a value between 0 and 1. ▪ Time interpolations: The source data is available between 2000 and 2018, which we interpolate to our grid using a nearest neighbour interpolation.
Human Footprint	1	<p>Human activities are one of the main sources of fire ignition. There are several ways of quantifying human influence, for example distance from major roadways, population density and urban/cultivated land cover types. The Human Footprint dataset combines such variables into a single index, which we use in the model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regridding: Polygon averaging into ignition grid cells. ▪ Time interpolation: Linear interpolation.
Lightning Strike Density	1	<p>Lightning strikes are also a contributor to fire ignition. Using satellite imagery, lightning strike flashes can be located and analysed. We use the WGLCC dataset to derive a gridded lightning strike density feature.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regridding: Bilinear interpolation ▪ Time interpolation: Nearest neighbour.
Elevation	1	<p>Elevation affects some variables such as atmospheric pressure. We use the</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regridding: Grid cell averages. ▪ Time interpolation: N/A Stationary dataset used.
Latitude	1	<p>Latitude can affect day length and phenology, amongst other things. We assign with every sample a latitude value. This provides one new feature.</p>

Validation

The model is tested by randomly splitting the data into three six-year splits. The model is trained on one split, calibrated on another and validated on the final split. This is repeated and the final ROC AUC score is calculated to be 0.92, which is excellent. Predicted probabilities are also compared to observed ignition distributions. This is shown in **Figure A1**.

Figure A1. Comparison of predicted probabilities against observed proportions. **a)** shows the cumulative sum (as a proportion of the total number of ignitions) at each predicted probability level. **b)** shows the predicted probabilities compared with observed proportions. Blue line shows the mean, dark shading shows where 50% of the data lies and light shading shows 90%.

For the vast majority of ignition events, the model performs well. On average, 90% of predicted probability lie within 15% of the true distribution. For example, a prediction of 10% will, with 90% confidence, correspond to a real distribution of between 8.5% and 11.5%. Predictions have little bias until predicted values of around 12% percent, however these events are very rare. In fact, over 90% of ignition events lie below 10% probability, and half of all ignition events lie under 3% probability. Once we reach 15% probability and below, almost all events are accounted for. This seems a little paradoxical, however it makes sense. High probability events and occurrences are much rarer events, and account for far fewer ignitions. Knowing this, the bias and higher spread at higher probabilities is less of a concern.

Data Reconstruction (2015–2018)

To get an estimate of how the model performs in time and space, we can reconstruct data for some period of time (2015–2018 here). We do not train the model on this period, only in 2001–2015. We can then inspect the reconstructed data and compare spatial and temporal patterns with those seen in the observations. **Figure A2** shows a comparison of the modeled and observed daily ignition probabilities during the 2015–2018 test period. The two distributions agree well with each other. This indicates that, generally speaking, the model performs well spatially over long periods of time.

Figure A2. Mean daily ignition probabilities for the testing period 2015–2018. Blue circle shows the location of Rio Branco. Blue circle shows the location of Rio Branco.

We must also investigate how well the model performs throughout the year, not just averaged over a three-year period. **Figure A3** shows the mean daily ignition probability during two months of the year: September and April. These two months are fire opposites, i.e., September generally sees the highest number of fire ignitions whereas April sees the lowest. Again, we see good agreement for both months between the modeled and observed distributions. Clearly, the probability of ignitions is lower throughout the domain in April than in September for both the model and observations—indicating that our model is doing more than simply replicating the average probability.

Figure A3. Modelled and observed mean daily ignition probabilities for two months: April (top) and September (bottom).

Model Sensitivity

We can test the sensitivity of our model to better understand how it reacts to changes in inputs. Here, we present two examples.

Figure A4 shows the mean response of the model to changes in FWI and Savanna proportion. Here, we see an increase in the probability (y-axis) of fire ignition as FWI increases. This agrees with what we would expect to see. The response is also non-linear. The probability of ignition increases more quickly for low values of FWI, slowing down for larger values. Similarly, as the proportion of savanna increases, so does ignition probability. This is also expected, as this land cover type is often drier, with shorter and sparser vegetation.

Figure A4. How does the model probability change with changes in inputs? These partial dependence plots attempt to quantify this. **Left:** Fire Weather Index. **Right:** Proportion of Savanna.

B. HYSPLIT Methodology

HYSPLIT is a model developed by NOAA and ARL. It is designed to do concentration and trajectory modeling for point source emissions, making it a good solution for fire smoke modeling. It is both Lagrangian and Eulerian approach. Put simply, the model works by releasing tracking points into the atmosphere, which it then pushes along (horizontally and vertically) using atmospheric data provided by the user. For trajectory analysis, a single point is “released,” pushed and followed. For concentration analysis, a large ensemble of points are released and tracked. These points also have some randomness applied to their movement to simulate real world dispersion in a plume of smoke. After the model is finished advecting our points, it counts them into geographical grid boxes to estimate concentrations.

Testing and Validation

To gain confidence in the use of our HYSPLIT configuration, we can compare output to real world observations. This is a vital step in the development and use of any model. For our trajectory analysis, we compare our output to satellite imagery, comparing the location of our trajectories against real life fire smoke plumes. We have used MODIS/Terra Corrected Reflectance data from 2022 to do this. Snapshots of satellites are chosen based on clarity of plumes. For a given satellite snapshot, we use fire locations identified by VIIRS which are approximately at the same time as our satellite snapshots. These locations are used for initializing trajectories. However, as we do not know the true start time of a given fire, we release trajectories for each during an eight-hour period prior to the earlier known detection by VIIRS. These are averaged into a single trajectory. The comparison will not be one-to-one here, as we are comparing a single trajectory (or the path of a single air

parcel) against an aggregate smoke plume. However, we will still be able to gain useful information, especially on the approximate direction a smoke plume takes.

Figure B1. Six examples of trajectories released in August and September of 2022 compared with satellite imagery of smoke plumes on the same day. Red dots show the VIIRS fire locations, colored dashed lines show the average 8-hour trajectory.

Figure B1 shows six trajectory validation examples. These are taken from four different locations around the domain and on four different days in August and September of 2022. The model performs well, getting the approximate direction of the trajectories correct in all cases. The trajectory follows the plumes especially well in the top two panels. In the bottom two panels, there are some deviations, however this is to be expected due to reasons discussed above.

Trajectory Analysis

In this study we employed a trajectory clustering analysis to 18 years of daily backwards trajectory, release at Rio Branco. A cluster analysis is a method for grouping together a large ensemble of trajectories in space and time. Fortunately, HYSPLIT comes packaged with a number of executables for doing this (see https://www.ready.noaa.gov/documents/Tutorial/html/traj_cluseqn.html). The aim of the algorithm is to assign trajectories to clusters in such

a way as to minimize spatial variance within clusters and maximize the spatial variance between clusters. In other words, trajectories within a cluster should be as similar as possible, but the average cluster trajectories should be as different as possible.

For the clustering algorithm, a number of clusters must be provided by the user. There is no true “correct” number of clusters to use and each trajectory could be defined as its own cluster. Methods exist to find numbers of clusters that split the total spatial variance significantly. For this study we used the method recommended for HYSPLIT. All possible numbers of trajectories are assessed and their TSV (Total Spatial Variance) is calculated. The gradient in TSV is then estimated and the largest value is chosen to identify the number of clusters. In our case, seven clusters were identified.

C. Scalability of the methodologies used in this paper

There are a number of components involved in the methodology presented in this paper. It is desirable that they can be scaled and reapplied to other regions. Here, we briefly outline our thoughts on the feasibility of fast application of these methods.

1. **Present day air quality observations.** These are obtained from either a single global dataset or the AQLI dataset (for life expectancies). In both cases, it is a simple case of data retrieval. For the gridded data, the nearest location to a set of points, or a region can be extracted quickly. The AQLI dataset provides state and sub-state scale estimates of life expectancy impact that can be quickly obtained.

2. **FiredPy fire distributions.** FiredPy has event polygons ready for every country on earth up until 2021. Up until this year, the data can be quickly obtained and analyzed using code in the github repository provided at the top of this report. After this point, the FiredPy model will have to be run manually. This is not a slow process however (on the country level).
3. **HYSPLIT backward trajectory analysis.** This can be quick. The HYSPLIT ensemble can be run using a single script. All that needs modifying in this script is the desired latitude and longitude. A small toolbox has been prepared in Python for then gridding trajectories in the ways shown in this paper. Although this step is not as quick as data retrieval, it is still scalable and quick.
4. **Machine learning fire events.** The full code used to train, test and apply the machine learning models presented is available in the github repository at the top of this document. Reapplying this to other areas requires a shape file and some bespoke data files. These can be downloaded from various online repositories. As the data expected by the framework is known, the data search does not take long. Although, download can take on the order of hours-1 day, depending on how busy download servers are. Training and validation could take up to an additional 1-2 days. The main potential problem with this analysis is that there is no guarantee that the model will be trained sufficiently (although it was acceptable in the three cases presented here). Additionally, as the framework is set up now, most of the system is semi-automatic except for the tuning step, which must be done manually.

D. Limitations & Future Work

As with any analysis, there are a number of limitations associated with the analyses presented in this paper. It is important to understand what these are and how they may affect the results. We can also view these limitations in a positive light: they provide opportunities for future work and improve our analyses even further.

Observations

Our methodology identified only the density of fire ignition events, and not their characteristics. How long a wildfire lasts, how far it spreads and the type of fuel that it burns are all critical factors when considering pollutant emissions. These limits place fundamental constraints on all of the analyses in this paper: observed fires, training our machine learning model, and subsequent projections all use this data. Future analyses should attempt to take these extra properties into consideration. The FiredPy tool used in this paper can also be used to identify area burned, burn rates and event durations. There are also other tools and datasets available which could be of use, for example the Global Fire Emissions Database (<https://www.globalfiredata.org>) and Global Fire Assimilation System (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/dataset/global-fire-assimilation-system>).

HYSPLIT Simulations

A HYSPLIT trajectory follows the path of a single air parcel (forwards or backwards), however it does not model phenomena such as dispersion of particles, mixing of air parcels, atmospheric residence time or chemistry. Dispersion and mixing may be partially accounted for by the 20-year ensemble approach taken in this study. Our approach also does not provide estimates of concentrations of pollutants in the air, hence why in this study we talk only in terms of “upstream fires.” A next step in this work is to improve upon our backwards trajectory analysis using a backwards concentration analysis at Rio Branco (still using HYSPLIT). This works similarly to our trajectory analysis, only an

ensemble of tracers are released each day, rather than a single trajectory. This would be able to account for dispersion and atmospheric residence time, although these parameters would still need to be chosen.

Even using backwards concentration simulations instead of trajectories does not provide direct estimates of pollutant concentrations or how they will change in the future. HYSPLIT is capable of doing full forward concentration simulations, which would include advection by the air, atmospheric residence times and dispersion. However, the model still does not include chemistry and its output can be arbitrary in its units. Despite this, an important next step for this work would be to run a full ensemble of fire smoke simulations, using either observed or projected locations as emission points. This could provide actual concentration estimates at Rio Branco and, by separating separate fire runs, could provide additional information of which areas contribute the most smoke. However, there are significant challenges associated with this approach. The fire observations and projections we have used in this study only describe the number of events per year in geographical grid cells. To perform a full forwards concentration ensemble accurately, we would need to estimate the duration of fires, size of fires, emission rate, plume height (from heat estimates) and fuel type. Many of these variables are available for the present period, and it may be possible to project into the future by randomly sampling these values from geographical bins. Alternatively, a framework that includes emission modeling, such as BlueSky (<https://portal.airfire.org>) could be used.

Machine Learning Model

There are a number of ways this machine learning model could potentially be improved. For example, separating FWI into its constituent components (temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, wind speed) may help the model to account for complex interactions not captured by the unitless FWI. Although we provided land cover types, the model has no way of estimating land cover dynamics, which could be a driver of fire risk. This could be done simply by using the annual change in land cover, or by providing deforestation, land use or tree loss datasets. It is also important to note that the predictions made by the machine learning model may be underestimated due to fire events missed by the satellite data.

For this study, we only considered projected fire counts based on changes in FWI. These changes were derived from dynamically downscaled CMIP5 projections using the RCP85 scenario. While this scenario implies very high levels of emissions it was deemed more realistic than RCP26, the only other IPCC scenario simulated with REMO2015. What's more, the time periods used can be understood as warming levels; with 2000-2020, 2040-2060 and 2070-2090 corresponding to a 1°C, 2°C, and slightly over 3°C world respectively. The latter two warming levels are plausible outcomes given current levels of emissions and climate policy. In our machine learning we used land cover and human footprint information static at the year 2000 or 2020 throughout the projection. Future applications of this model could include projecting fire counts for hypothetical future land cover distributions, beyond those implied in IPCC scenarios, with varying levels of deforestation and urban development.

WOODWELL CLIMATE RESEARCH CENTER (“Woodwell Climate”) conducts science for solutions at the nexus of climate, people and nature. We partner with leaders and communities for just, meaningful impact to address the climate crisis. Our scientists helped to launch the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in 1992, and in 2007, Woodwell scientists shared the Nobel Prize awarded to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. For over 35 years, Woodwell has combined hands-on experience and policy impact to identify and support societal-scale solutions that can be put into immediate action. This includes working with municipalities on the frontlines of the climate crisis.

149 Woods Hole Road, Falmouth, MA 02540 USA ■ +1 508-540-9900 ■ woodwellclimate.org